

Table 1. Media composition for DRGs microfluidic culture.

DIV	Somal compartment 200 μ L/well		AXONAL compartment 100 μ L/well	
DIV 0	Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%
	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (promega)	100 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
DIV 1	Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%
	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (promega)	50 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	50 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (sigma)	17.5 μ g/mL	Uridine (sigma)	17.5 μ g/mL
	5-Fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (sigma)	7.5 μ g/mL	5-Fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (sigma)	7.5 μ g/mL
DIV 3	Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium (Gibco)	
DIV 5	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (gibco)	1%
	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%	B27 supplement (gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%	Penicillin-streptomycin (gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (sigma)	17.5 μ g/mL	Uridine (sigma)	17.5 μ g/mL
	5-Fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (sigma)	7.5 μ g/mL	5-Fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (sigma)	7.5 μ g/mL

females and males (Figure S2, Tables S4 and S5). Trigeminal sensory neurons were also amenable to culture in MFCs and exhibited a similar functionality than their DRG counterparts (Figure 4).

Keratinocytes interact with axonal sensory endings and modulate their activity

Co-culturing axonal sensory endings with keratinocytes (HaCaT cells), in the presence of 100 ng/mL nerve growth factor (NGF) and 100 ng/mL glial derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) and the absence of 5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine to maintain keratinocyte viability (Table S1, Figure S3), resulted in a strong physical interaction between sensory endings and keratinocytes as revealed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (Figure 2(g)). Electron microscopy images show that peripheral ends form synapse-like contacts with HaCaT cells (Figure 2(h)) or by-pass a particular cell to interact with another as it occurs in the epidermis (Figure 2(i)). Under these conditions up to 70% of neurons extended axons through the microchannels.

Stimulation of the axonal compartment with 40 mM KCl resulted in Ca^{2+} transients in the soma of 70.2% of neurons (Figures 2(j) and (k)). Further analysis revealed that 27.4% of Did'-labelled neurons responded to 100 nM capsaicin, 31.5% to 100 μ M menthol, 24.4% to 100 μ M AITC (Figure 2(l)), 5% to capsaicin and menthol, 6% to menthol and AITC and 4.4% to capsaicin and AITC (Figure S3). Notably, a higher percentage of neurons responded to capsaicin, menthol and AITC than in the absence of keratinocytes (Figure 2(b),

Figure S3, Table S6) and this effect were not due to the medium change in the axonal compartment with respect to the DRGs MFC culture (Table S7). MFC-based DRG cultures and of neurons co-cultured with keratinocytes were exposed to the same NGF and GDNF concentrations to have a comparable neurotrophic effect (Table 1, Table S1). Nonetheless, as human keratinocytes secrete NGF,³⁵ we cannot exclude that secreted NGF affects neuronal endings length, excitability and thermoTRPs expression.^{36,37} The magnitude of the normalized responses was not significantly altered by the presence of the HaCaT cells. These results indicate that keratinocytes increased the number of peripheral ends expressing functional thermoTRPs as well as exhibiting K^+ -dependent excitability, suggesting a paracrine increase in axonal growth through microchannels along with a modulation of peripheral endings functionality.

Inflammatory sensitization and resolution of peripheral terminals

Next, we set to validate the microfluidic nociceptor culture as a model to study inflammatory sensitization. We exposed axonal endings to an inflammatory soup or vehicle at DIV five for 24 h (Table S2), and neuronal activity was recorded at DIV six and DIV 8 (0 h and 48 h post insult) to investigate inflammatory sensitization and its resolution. Note that inflammatory mediators reversibly reduced axonal density (Figure S4). Functionally, axonal endings appear to be more active after inflammatory sensitization (Figures 5(a)-(C)), as reflected by the 2-fold increment in the percentage of neurons